

Chemical Examination of the Bark of *Luvunga scandens*, Ham

Buddha Dev Paul and P. K. Bose

Taraxerol, myricardiol and myricolal have been found to be present in the bark of *Luvunga scandens*.

The berries of *Luvunga scandens* Ham. (Fam. Rutaceae) are extensively used in Ayurvedic system of medicine¹. The presence of xanthotoxin, xanthyletin, isopimpinellin and luvangetin in them has been reported².

We have now subjected the bark to chemical examination. Extraction of the powdered bark with light petroleum and subsequent chromatography of the extracted material furnished a colourless crystalline product A, m.p. 267°, which gave a positive Liebermann-Burchard test and a yellow colour with tetranitromethane solution, thus indicating that it might be a triterpenoid.

Benzene extract of the defatted bark yielded, after repeated crystallisations from alcohol, colourless crystals of product B, m.p. 262-63°. Like product A, it responded to Liebermann-Burchard and tetranitromethane tests.

The C-H values of product B agreed with the formula $C_{30}H_{50}\pm_nO_n$. It formed a diacetyl derivative, m.p. 248°, from which the parent compound could be regenerated by alkaline hydrolysis. Thin-layer chromatography gave only one spot and hence it was assumed to be homogeneous. The infra-red spectrum revealed the presence of alcoholic OH (bands at 3450 cm^{-1}), gem-dimethyl (1360, 1378 cm^{-1}), primary hydroxyl (1080 cm^{-1}) and an unsaturated centre $>C=CH-$ (810 cm^{-1}). Sarett oxidation of the compound furnished the compound (IV), m.p. 227-8° which gave a positive Zimmermann reaction³ for 3-keto group. The UV spectrum of the ketone is not in conformity with a conjugated ketone. The IR spectrum included peaks at 1725 ($=CHO$); 1700 ($>CO$); 1360, 1376 (gem-dimethyl) and 811 cm^{-1} ($>C=CH-$). Hence it was inferred that one of the alcoholic groups is secondary and the other primary.

To have some idea about the basic skeleton of the diketone it was subjected to Huang-Minlon reduction to yield a hydrocarbon, m.p. 241°, which was found to be identical with taraxerene⁴ (II) obtained from taraxerol (I). The identity was established through the comparison of their m.p., m.m.p., I.R. spectra and by T. L. C.

1. Kirtikar, K.R. and Basu, B.D., *Indian Medicinal Plants*, Vol. 1, p. 479. (1933).

2. Bose, P. K. and Mukherjee, A., *This Journal*, 1944, 21, 181.

3. D. H. R. Barton and P. de Mayo, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 887.

4. J. L. Simonsen and W. C. J. Ross, *The Terpenes*, 1957, Vol. IV, p. 276. Cambridge University Press, London.

Since the substance B has the basic skeleton of taraxerol, it was expected that its diacetate would undergo non-synchronous isomerization to an amyrin system under the influence of hydrochloric (mineral) acid. This isomerization would involve the rings C and D as follows

FIG. 1

This expectation has been realised and the resulting product has been found to be identical with erythrodiol diacetate (m.p., m.m.p., I.R., T.L.C.).

The compound B, therefore, has the structure (III) which is the same as that of myricardiol⁵, m.p. 273-4°, obtained from bark of *Myrica gale* by Ryabinin and Matyukhina. A direct comparison of the two compounds has not been possible.

Product A, m.p. 287°, gave two spots in T.L.C. Attempts to separate the constituents as such, or through their acetyl derivatives by crystallization or column chromatography resulted in failure. Preparative T.L.C. also failed, as the two spots were very close to each other.

Product A showed the following peaks in the IR spectrum: 3600 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl); 1737 cm^{-1} (aldehyde); 1360—1380 cm^{-1} (gem-dimethyl) and 810 cm^{-1} (double bond $>\text{C}=\text{CH}\cdot$).

As Zimmermann test with product A was negative, it was presumed that it was an inseparable mixture of an aldehyde and the corresponding methyl compound. This presumption is justified by the fact that on borohydride reduction a product was obtained which no longer showed the -CHO band in the IR spectrum. This reduction product, however, gave two spots on T.L.C., corresponding to taraxerol (I) and myricardiol (III). Hence, product A is presumed to be a mixture of taraxerol (I) and the corresponding C_{30} -aldehyde (V), a known triterpene, named myricolal⁶, also obtained from the bark of *Myrica gale*⁶.

- (I) Taraxerol, $\text{R}_1=\text{OH}$, $\text{R}_2=\text{CH}_3$ in Fig. 2
- (II) Taraxerene, $\text{R}_1=\text{H}$, $\text{R}_2=\text{CH}_3$
- (III) Myricardiol, $\text{R}_1=\text{OH}$, $\text{R}_2=\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$
- (IV) Myriconal, $\text{R}_1=\text{O}$, $\text{R}_2=\text{CHO}$
- (V) Myricolal, $\text{R}_1=\text{OH}$, $\text{R}_2=\text{CHO}$

FIG. 2

- 5. A. A. Ryabinin and L. G. Matyukhina, *Doklady Akad. Nauk S. S. S. R.* 1959, 129, 125.
- 6. I. G. Matyukhina and A. A. Ryabinin, *Doklady Akad. Nauk, S. S. S. R.* 1959, 131, 316.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Isolation of substance A: Air-dried powdered bark (1.5 kg.) of *Luvunga scandens* was extracted with petroleum-ether under reflux for 32 hr. Complete removal of the solvent left a yellow solid mass. It was leached twice with cold petroleum ether (75 ml. $\times$ 2). The remaining insoluble mass in benzene was chromatographed over alumina (200 g.). Elution with petroleum ether—benzene (1 : 3, 150 ml.) and subsequent crystallisations of the residue from benzene—petroleum ether yielded substance A (0.120 g.) as needles, m.p. 267°. Thin layer chromatography showed that it was a mixture of two compounds.

Isolation of substance B: The defatted bark was then extracted under reflux with benzene for 32 hr. and the solvent removed. The residual sticky mass was leached with warm chloroform (three times) when a white amorphous mass was left. It was dissolved in hot alcohol and filtered. The alcohol-soluble part on concentration and cooling to room temperature deposited light colourless crystals (0.5 g.). The substance was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol until it was homogeneous to thin-layer chromatography (benzene: chloroform: methanol: 55:40:1; spraying reagent H_2SO_4/Ac_2O); m.p. 262-3°. (Found: C, 81.10; H, 11.66. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{30}O_4$: C, 81.39; H, 11.38%).

Acetylation of Product B: The substance B (100 mg.) was dissolved in hot pyridine (25 ml.) and to it was added acetic anhydride (25 ml.). The mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 3 hr., cooled, filtered and the crystals were washed thoroughly with distilled water. Subsequent recrystallisation of the product from benzene—pet. ether yielded the diacetate as needles, m.p. 248° (Found: C, 77.41; H, 9.95. Calc. for $C_{34}H_{34}O_6$: C, 77.52; H, 10.33%).

Deacetylation of the above product: The diacetyl derivative (50 mg.) was dissolved in methanolic potassium hydroxide (7%, 30 ml.) and refluxed for 3 hr. Methanol was removed on a steam-bath maintaining the concentration of alkali by addition of distilled water. The separated mass was filtered and crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 262-3°, mixed m.p. 262°. It proved to be identical with the parent substance in comparative thin-layer chromatography.

Chromic acid oxidation of substance B: The substance B (100 mg.) in cold pyridine (25 ml.) was treated with chromium trioxide-pyridine complex (made from 140 mg. chromium trioxide and 5 ml. pyridine) at 0-4°. The mixture at once turned orange-red. It was shaken for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and left overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). The chloroform-soluble residue was taken up in benzene and filtered through a column of alumina and washed down with petroleum ether-benzene (1:1, 50 ml.). Crystallisation of the product from alcohol furnished the keto-aldehyde (IV) as prisms, m.p. 227-8°. It gave positive Zimmermann test.

Wolff-Kishner (modified Huang-Minlon) reduction of the above compound: To a solution of the keto-aldehyde (200 mg.) in xylene-alcohol mixture (5 ml. each) was added diethylene glycol (7 ml.). The mixture was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (85%, 6 ml.)

*All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Petroleum-ether refers to fraction b.p. 40-60°, and alumina used for chromatography is of Brockmann's (E. Merck) grade. Samples for analysis were dried in vacuo over phosphorus pentoxide at 80° for 12 hr.

in a paraffin bath for 2 hr. Solid potassium hydroxide (1.5 g.) was added to the mixture, and the distillation started to remove alcohol, xylene and excess hydrazine hydrate. The distillation was continued until the temperature rose to 190°. The reaction mixture was then heated under reflux at 198-200° for 4½ hr. It was cooled, poured on crushed ice and extracted with ether. The ether-soluble residue was taken up in benzene and filtered through a column of alumina and washed down with petroleum ether-benzene (1:2, 100 ml.). Crystallisation of the product from the same solvent gave the hydrocarbon as prisms (120 mg.), m.p. 241°. Taraxerene prepared from taraxerol following the above mentioned procedure had the same m.p. The mixed m.p. was 241-2°. The two substances were found to be identical in thin-layer chromatography.

Isomerisation of diacetate of substance B to erythrodiol diacetate: The diacetate (25 mg.) was dissolved in warm acetic acid (5 ml.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.5 ml.) The mixture was heated on a steam bath for 10 min. It was then poured on crushed ice and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was then washed thoroughly with distilled water, dried and evaporated out. The residue was taken up in benzene and poured into a column of 10% acid-washed alumina. The column was eluted with petroleum ether-benzene (1:2, 50 ml.) and the residue from the eluate was crystallised from aqueous methanol as needles, m.p. 185°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of m.p. 185°; 185-6°. The products were identical in comparative thin-layer chromatography.

The authors thank Dr D. M. Bose, Director, Bose Institute, and Dr. A. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry, for the facilities given. One of us (B.D.P.) is indebted to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for the grant of a scholarship.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT
BOSE INSTITUTE
CALCUTTA 9.

Received, March 31, 1967.